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Cultivating a Global Mentality Virtue Ethics for an Age of Globalization

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Abstract: Cultivating a global mentality is a contemporary need with a view to the formation of good habits or virtues necessary for co-existence in the present situation of globalization. Rather than providing a critique of globalization in terms of whether it is leading towards integral development or not (a method more suited along the lines of a deontological or teleological ethics), the author has preferred to adopt an approach more in keeping with virtue ethics. Accordingly, he has focused on the cultivation of key virtues which are not only necessary to survive in this new age of globalization, but also to flourish in such a world. Furthermore, the cultivation of these virtues is with a view to guiding the processes of development along more salubrious lines. The virtues chosen are the following: dialogical pluralism, creative visualization, collaborative solidarity, transnational responsibility and pro-active optimism. A basic theme which underlies the discussion is the role of religion in this contemporary situation, and how religion has the power to cultivate these virtues so as to flourish within such a world and also to guide such a world towards integral personal and social development.

Key Words: Globalization, global capitalism, religion, integral development, virtue ethics

This is an essay in *virtue ethics* applied to the phenomenon of globalization and social development, guided by the role and influence of religion. I intend to present the basic virtues or elements of an appropriate practical mentality or disposition necessary in order to both experience personal and social well-being (*eudaimonia*) in the current scenario of globalization and to orient global processes towards integral social development using adequate practical wisdom (*phronesis*).

In order to both experience personal fulfilment within our contemporary world of globalization and to make this world more humane and harmonious, one needs an adequate social and moral education – an education which virtue ethics is better suited to provide as compared to *deontological* and *teleological* ethical schools of thought.¹ There is a considerable amount of literature available with regard to critical perspectives relating to the merits and demerits of globalization from a deontological or teleological position. From a deontological position (which is largely concerned with rules and duties), one can provide a critique of globalization in terms of whether its processes and products are *in principle* suitable or detrimental to human nature and social relations (i.e, whether they are right or wrong). From a teleological position (which is largely concerned with social consequences), one can provide a critique of globalization in terms of whether it is *ultimately or proximately socially beneficial or destructive* (i.e, whether they are good or bad).² Compared to these deontological and teleological perspectives, there is comparatively little literature available with regard to the adoption or the cultivation of relevant virtues which would serve to better prepare ourselves to live in an increasingly globalized world. Such an approach is necessary, so as to both enjoy the benefits of globalization and to necessarily guide, to the best of our ability, the shape globalization will take in the future.

The Context of our Discussion

We live in a world of increasing globalization. We also live in a world where religion seems to be playing a more significant role in the public sphere, for better or worse. The challenge before us is to orient both globalization and religious currents – separately and con-

nectedly – into more productive channels in terms of social development.³ By ‘religion’ I do not include only the mainstream organized systems of faith, but indeed any organized or relatively unorganized movement which is governed by a set of meanings, values, beliefs and rituals based on a transcendent reality. By ‘globalization’ I do not just include transnational eco-political processes, but the whole gamut of a transnational exchange of goods, services, capital, knowledge, values and lifestyle. The more specifically eco-political aspect of globalization may be termed ‘global capitalism,’ which is a movement mainly concerned with the development of a transnational system of liberal, market-driven trade, which is of course influenced and restricted by global political currents.

In *Making Globalization Good: The Moral Challenges of Global Capitalism* – a seminal work closely related to the theme of this essay⁴ – John Dunning, the editor, defines globalization as:

*the connectivity of individuals and institutions across the globe, or at least, over most of it. Such connectivity may be shallow or deep; short or long lasting. It may be geared to advancing personal or institutional interests; and economic, cultural, or political goals . . . Globalization is a morally neutral concept. In itself, it is neither good nor bad, but it may be motivated for good or bad reasons, and used to bring about more or less good or bad results. (original italics)*⁵

The concept of ‘global capitalism,’ as has been pointed out, is relatively more restrictive, as it has to do primarily with eco-political maneuvering. It is thus ideologically more problematic, as it is rooted in traditional economic presuppositions and practices which have given rise to the current eco-political imbalance within and between nations. However, as a contemporary adage goes, “capitalism is the worst economic system on the face of the earth, except for all of the other alternatives!” In contrast to this more narrow concept of ‘global capitalism’, Dunning proposes a wider and richer concept of ‘responsible global capitalism’ (RGC), which

includes the set of non-market institutions within which the market is embedded and which, together, characterize a global society . . . it is the task of these institutions to set the rules and monitor the behaviour

of markets; to engage in a variety of market facilitating and/or regulatory activities; and to produce such socially desirable products, which, left unaided, the market is unable or unwilling to produce. RGC then is a system made up of individuals, private commercial corporations, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), governments, and supranational agencies. Each has a unique and critical role to play. (original italics)⁶

A virtue ethics suited for the world of globalization would need to be cultivated within this matrix of personal, social, governmental, non-governmental and corporate responsibility. Joseph Stiglitz too advocates this “more holistic approach to development . . . Such an approach should embrace a social, moral and environmental dimension as well as an economic one.”⁷

There is no doubt that we are living today in a situation of increasing globalization (and increasing global capitalism), and it appears that we will continue to do so in the near future. There are two primary responses to such a situation. One is to fight the processes of globalization, especially those processes which are based on ‘neoliberal’ eco-political policies leading to apparently draconian ‘structural adjustment policies’ which seem to harm weaker nations and peoples. The second is to channelize the social energies which globalization has released along productive and integrally developmental pathways, including that of maximizing the possibilities for transnational fair trade. This essay will adopt the logic of the second alternative, for two main reasons:

Firstly, at a more realistic level, I do not see any viable and widespread alternative to globalization – and its attendant global capitalism – gaining international currency. The past couple of decades have seen the collapse of communism as a viable eco-political alternative. Even China has pragmatically given way (economically, if not politically) to primarily capitalist means of production and distribution. The Communists today in West Bengal are also struggling to come to terms with this reality.

Secondly, I see that globalization, in spite of its many drawbacks, has the potential to raise humanity to a new level of consciousness, so as to shake off the shackles of much of debilitating tradition and

replace them with more emancipatory mentalities. Also, responsible globalization has the potentiality to overcome artificial problems such as famine, hunger, epidemics, illiteracy and war, among other human-made problems. Here it is good to recognize that the strengths of globalization may also be considered to be its weaknesses, even though we may attempt to make it a responsible process. For example, even in a situation of fair trade, global capitalism could lead to job insecurity, for jobs can move overnight to locations favouring more lucrative production opportunities (this is certainly adversely affecting citizens of more economically developed nations today). At the cultural level, openness to transnational cultures may lead to the gradual erosion of one's more traditionally salubrious cultural values. One may be more influenced to adopt lifestyles, relationships and commitments which are easy, convenient and gratifying, rather than those which are more substantial, wholesome and longer-lasting. This in turn will play out at the economic level in terms of a focus on the production of needless sophisticated consumer goods instead of more wholesome and cheaper sustainable-oriented goods and services which are relatively of greater benefit for those more socially disadvantaged. For these and other reasons, globalization and (economic, political, and cultural) marginalization may well go hand in hand for some time to come.⁸

It is debatable, however, whether the contemporary processes of globalization are the *causes* of this marginalization or the potential *solutions* of impoverishment and marginalization. A substantial amount of the literature with regard to the current state of social development is rather polarized, depending largely upon the agency and individuals presenting the material, and the parameters or criteria being considered. As a result, value-laden theories and instruments of investigation give rise to ridiculously different social scenarios, ranging from a frenzied apocalyptic rally call at the one end, to annunciations of the Kingdom of Heaven on earth itself at the other. The former clarion call is usually issued by singularly anti-MNC⁹ NGOs, while the latter acclamation is enunciated by a good number of corporate and management gurus who seem to worship unashamedly and uncritically at the shrine of opulence. Such a polarized situation is unhelpful, even though partially unavoidable, for exaggerated rhetoric unfortunately still remains one of the most pow-

erful tools for social mobilization.¹⁰ Keeping these excesses in mind, I will instead attempt to adopt a comparatively conciliatory, practical and realistic approach in this essay.

Globalization has to do with integral social development, somewhat matching the purpose and direction of the different religions, which are concerned with salvation or personal and communitarian wholeness or integrity (Latin 'salvus,' Greek 'holos,' and Sanskrit 'sarvam'). Today, the influence of religion seems to be on the ascendancy with regard to contemporary social processes. The task before us is to channelize religious interests and forces so that salubrious processes of globalization are fostered and less healthy processes are challenged and overcome. Sustained religious instruction and education could well provide the foundations for an adequate virtue ethics in such a situation. The role of religion is pivotal in the development of these virtues simply because of the power which religious organizations and movements have over the minds and hearts of billions of human beings worldwide.

We will now focus on the specific virtues or dispositions or attitudes governing practical action which need to be cultivated in this world of globalization. These attitudes are necessary not only to help one to survive in such a world, but hopefully more than that, to thrive in such a world, and even more, to act responsibly so as to guide processes of development towards a more integrated pattern of personal and social well-being (*eudaimonia*). I have chosen five prominent virtues, viz., *dialogical pluralism, creative visualization, collaborative solidarity, transnational responsibility and pro-active optimism*. These are by no means an exhaustive list of virtues necessary for our contemporary world, but they seem to be some of the more basic ones, both on a personal as well as on a communitarian level. Also, these are not virtues to be cultivated mainly by the more privileged beneficiaries of globalization, so that they may further benefit from these processes of globalization, but instead by each and every member of the human community, even those who are at present the victims of globalization, so that they may better prepare themselves to be victims no more.¹¹

1. Dialogical Pluralism

Perhaps one of the more helpful insights of 'post-modern' thought is that every metanarrative or worldview is a partial, limited perspective which needs to be complemented by other perspectives. It would be too much for religious believers and even believers in any form of developmental work to go along with Lyotard's more radical suggestion of an adoption, along post-modern lines, of "an incredulity toward metanarratives." For no individual or institution engaged in developmental work could truly be said to be free of the power and influence of some form of 'ideology,' or in terms of a temporal construction, a 'metanarrative. Indeed metanarratives are not only the consequent construction of a community's search for truth, but concomitantly serve as powerful means of motivation towards personal and social development. Thus, instead of a rejection or a forfeiting of these metanarratives (an act which would do violence to the human spirit), what would prove to be more helpful and productive is a concerted strategy of *dialogical pluralism* between the adherents who live by these metanarratives. Negatively, dialogical pluralism entails the readiness to renounce any form of aggressive dogmatism or fundamentalism associated with these grand narratives, be it socio-political, cultural or religious. Positively, dialogical pluralism is an attitude which is aimed at cultivating at the very least a basic tolerance of the 'other' (community), with a more ultimate objective of fostering a deeper respect for the 'other.' J. Orstrom Moller provides us with a helpful and somewhat comprehensive understanding of tolerance:

Tolerance does not mean opening the floodgates for everybody to behave as they like. Tolerance means the right to think and act differently from other people but within a mutually agreed framework . . . Thinking in this way opens the door for realizing that what is best for us may not necessarily be best for others. And that gives birth to the crucial observation that the heart of tolerance is that we care for other people's destiny even if we do not agree with them.¹²

Tolerance, then, is not an excuse or condition for relativistic thinking. A globalized world cannot afford such a luxury, especially since we are compelled to interrelate with different peoples in different social circumstances. An educated tolerance rather entails the virtue of humility, viz., a recognition of the limitedness of one's perspective with regard to personal and social development. This in turn entails the necessity of the creation of an adequate hermeneutical (interpretive) and social space for the 'other' to function and relate, while at the same time sharing a common social space ("within a mutually agreed framework," according to Moller).

The full flowering of this virtue of tolerance is thus the virtue of respect for the other, and if this respect is genuine, what will necessarily follow is the desire to borrow from the wellsprings of the other. For even if we do not entirely agree with the perspective of the other, there are surely some aspects of the worldview of the other which may be incorporated into one's own paradigm or way of life. Respect, then, is not just a recognition of the validity of the 'other,' but a conscious desire to interact with the other in order to both learn from and contribute towards each other's development. The foundation of these virtues of tolerance, humility and respect is human relationships – not just the formal relationships constructed at forums of interreligious or intercultural dialogue, but informal relationships with one's neighbour at home and at work, and, in a situation of globalization, this may mean with one's neighbour living halfway around the globe.

Globalization has the potentiality to raise us all beyond the 'we' versus 'them' discourse. This discourse is based on a narrow understanding of the self as belonging to one primary community. In fact, as Amartya Sen convincingly argues, a sense of multiple-identity is both true to a phenomenological description of our being-in-the-world, as well as is a powerful means of overcoming communally divisive ideological forces.¹³ As a matter of fact, we belong to different communities – not just religious, but also national, ethnic, regional, class, caste, occupational, guild, neighbourhood, sportsclub, etc. To identify ourselves with one primary community seems to belie all other identifications. Furthermore, even if this is widespread, and in some sense inevitable, because of primary in-

doctrination and social pressure, it is unfortunate that these forms of identification sometimes result in inter-communal strife and even violence. Indeed, Sen's interest in pursuing this topic initially arose from a first-hand witness of the bloody interreligious violence in West Bengal during his childhood.

Religious sentiments have played a powerful role in fermenting interreligious strife, often linked with political interests, and based upon fundamentalist religious and inadequate secular education. But religion can also play a powerful role in reversing this trend, and in fostering a spirit of interreligious dialogical pluralism. The virtue of pluralism leading to respect for the other is not an optional luxury but a pressing necessity, especially as interreligious relations will only become more intense with the increase of global trade and exchange at different levels. This means a greater openness to as well as a greater challenge between adherents of the different religions to reinterpret their respective religions in more salubrious terms, not only for themselves, but for the sake of the common good. In the long run, and even in the short, this virtue will help religious practitioners and the human community in general not only to experience peace between the different communities, but more so, to make progress as one borrows from one another's traditions. A reinterpretation of the past is necessary if one has to move towards a peaceful and prosperous future – which brings us to the next of our shortlisted virtues, viz. creative visualization.

2. Creative Visualization

Perhaps one of the most important virtues to develop in this new age of globalization is that of creative thinking or creative visualization. Those individuals and institutions ready for significant 'paradigm shifts' will survive, while those who refuse to emerge from their comfort zones and modify their traditional ways of thinking and doing will likely have to struggle to survive. For the only thing one can be certain about in the world of globalization is that it is characterized by change.

Perhaps the most significant change that has been brought about in our world over the last two decades is the possibility of instant and widespread communication via the internet. Primarily on ac-

count of the power and omnipresence of the internet, each one of us is increasingly capable of raising global levels of creativity. This is already happening in terms of projects undertaken by TNCs which span whole continents and which thus enable an almost uninterrupted '24/7' work schedule. But besides this, creativity in terms of productive solutions for current problems is considerably enhanced, because projects placed on the internet are being increasingly transnationally executed by faceless and even nameless individuals, and often for little or no remuneration.¹⁴

The communication revolution in general has brought the world much closer, not only at the level of multinational business conferences and sophisticated scientific (medical/engineering) ventures, but even at the very ordinary level of cell-phone conversation which allows very small scale entrepreneurs like the streetside vegetable seller to optimize his or her sales. The days of state-controlled media in most nations is a thing of the past, as it has become well-nigh impossible for totalitarian regimes to successfully employ strategies of media-censoring or to disseminate monopolistic propaganda. Indeed, conventional media sources too stand threatened on account of the power of omnipresent 'bloggers' who are capable of operating more independently with regard to the reporting and analysis of events.

Knowledge and the 'service' industry in general has replaced goods and manufacturing as the key ingredient in any fast-growing economy. Today India has an edge in this sector simply because of the number of skilled workers available. For the moment, at least, we are capitalizing on the English-based educational infrastructure of the past. But this situation could change overnight, unless one is ready not only to be trained adequately to perform specific skills, but to be trained to think creatively as well. What is already perceived is a dearth of competent CEOs for corporations which are currently driving the Indian economy. Soon there may be a vast amount of capital in India, but not enough creative visionaries and competent heads of organizations to sustain and drive economic growth.

Perhaps this virtue of creative visualization is most needed in international relations, for politics and economics are intrinsically

related. The new world order, pulled along headlong by the fast pace of global capitalism, cannot travel very far if political relations are sour and unstable. While it is true that the permanent members of the Security Council are paradoxically the world's largest producers and exporters of arms, this situation seems to belong to a logic of the past, when instability in a distant country did not affect these host nations which export war and its accoutrements. Today global terrorism which at its roots is a response to ecological rapaciousness and eco-political domination, has proved that this does not hold true any more.

For economic trade to flow smoothly, the logic of the future will need to be dominated by peaceful processes, and above all by processes not just of justice, but more so of reconciliation. Justice is often a necessary precondition for peace within and between nations, but sometimes justice does not prove sufficient. What is needed is to work towards deeper forms of consensus based upon reconciliation. Reconciliation requires creative visualization, because one needs to be able to retell or reinterpret the same story also from the sympathetic perspective of the 'other,' rather than purely from the more conventional, and often partisan, justice-oriented 'rights-duties' discourse. The 'Truth and Reconciliation Committee' experiment in South Africa, based more upon honest dialogue rather than incriminating discourse, provides us with a working model as to how this approach may better serve to bring about peace in our conflict-ridden world. Another example demonstrating the importance of this alternate logic of peace and reconciliation features in a joint letter framed by Archbishop Desmond Tutu and Amartya Sen with regard to the present political predicament in Myanmar:

Now that Burma is on the [Security] council's agenda, we urge the passage of a *nonpunitive resolution* that will serve as a baseline for freeing political prisoners, ceasing attacks against Burma's ethnic minorities, and promoting a political dialogue that will lead to the peace and freedom the overwhelming majority of the Burmese people have demanded. (italics mine)¹⁵

This is because thinking in terms of punitive resolutions (especially extreme ones like the execution of Saddam Hussain) belongs

to the logic of the past. This type of thinking, rather than resolving issues, only serves to fuel the cycle of violence. The new age requires leaders quite different from the ilk of the Bushes and Bin Ladens of our time.

In this area of creative visualization, especially as applied to processes of reconciliation within and between nations, religion clearly has a pivotal role to play. Religious texts need to be interpreted in more benign and contemporary terms that match the ethos of the day and are more forward-looking, rather than serve to reinforce old prejudices against other communities. Those religions which are able to appropriately reinterpret themselves will also be able to attract more followers, while those that do not will either be marginalized, disregarded, or worse, gain pariah status. If religions have to survive they will need to learn how to relate well with other religious traditions as well as how best to contribute towards common human welfare by adopting the common mindset of collaborative solidarity.

3. Collaborative Solidarity

During the period of the Cold War there were more rigid power blocks, including that of the relatively powerless Non-Aligned Movement. Today global capitalism has allowed for and even necessitated the emergence of strategic relationships which break down such rigid power divisions. Thus it is quite possible (though not always easy) to have political alliances with one nation while at the same time pursuing economic relations with a nation which is politically hostile to the first. This is what makes the present eco-political situation more complex, but also far less polarized. Global trade has necessitated the pursuit of these transideological relationships.

But global trade will also necessitate the promotion of the well-being and success of the other, whether the other is the friend or the enemy. This is not just for magnanimous reasons, but for reasons of survival to begin with, and furthermore for reasons of one's own prosperity. For if the other person or community succeeds and is prosperous in life, this in turn will lead to the production of better economic and political opportunities for all. An enlightened global-

ization will not merely allow for the success of the other, but positively desire the success of the other. The present Indian government has realized, for example (beyond obvious politically strategic reasons), that if the country has to make progress, the most backward communities will simultaneously need to progress as well. Hence, based on the recommendations of the Sachar Commission Report, the present Government wants the Muslims of our country to be better educated and emancipated, so as to more suitably enter into and contribute towards the dynamics of nation-building.

This sense of partnership or collaborative solidarity is also called for in the area of interreligious relations. Religions have often arisen from quite different social contexts, and where they have arisen from the same context, they have sometimes had bloody pathways of separation. The time has come for the different religions (especially the mainstream ones) to learn to coexist together. The alternative is to live in disharmony – a state which should normally be antithetical to any religious tradition. This need for overcoming conflict and pursuing collaboration in interreligious relations is well brought out by the words of the summary statement of the ‘International Conference on Religion and Globalization’ held at Chiang Mai, Thailand, in 2003:

We in our respective religious communities can no longer afford to live in isolation, or with attitudes of exclusion or competition. We acknowledge the continuing need to reexamine our religious traditions and institutions, so that religion, rather than being part of the problem, can serve as a source of empowerment and enlightenment as we seek for solutions [to the world’s problems].¹⁶

This partnership is an urgent need between religious believers who believe differently, but who need to work towards a more concerted effort in the resolution of global problems. The logic of superiority and domination needs to give way to the logic of partnership and solidarity. Furthermore, this solidarity needs to express itself not just in interreligious pathways, but more so in collaborative social action.

The various religions, with their vast international infrastructures, have the ability to radically alter the conditions necessary for eco-

conomic prosperity. Amartya Sen is one of those economists who recognizes the role of non-governmental forces in the creation of better educational and health resources in order to foster long-term economic growth. In the words of Sen,

As has been amply established in empirical studies, market outcomes are massively influenced by public policies in education, epidemiology, land reform, microcredit facilities, appropriate legal protections, et cetera; and *in each of these fields, there is work to be done through public action* that can radically alter the outcome of local and global economic relations. (italics mine)¹⁷

Rather than purely focus on the sacred and make religion purely an individualistic affair, religious leaders need to increasingly recognize the tremendous potential which religious organizations possess in terms of a contribution towards the economic welfare of the human family. This recognition, however, can only come about when one is open to develop a sense of transreligious and transnational responsibility, i.e., a sense of duty which does not terminate at the boundaries of one's religious or national community. When this happens, we will truly experience the full flowering of Teilhard de Chardin's 'noosphere' or global sense of interconnectedness.

4. Transnational Responsibility

Globalization necessarily calls into question traditional political boundaries and juridical paradigms. What we will increasingly witness is a gradual reduction of the power of solely national legislative, executive and juridical processes in favour of a transnational and hence a more just global forum for the preservation and expression of human rights. It seems that we have indeed entered into this new age of critical co-responsibility for our world, or, in other words, the age of the global citizen. This is not as yet a structured political experience, but it is already an experience of the new global polis (the new global city), reflected by TIME magazine, when it nominated the 'Person of the Year 2006' to be 'YOU,' i.e., each and every citizen of the world. By doing this, TIME wants to make the claim that the makers of human history are no more primarily the leaders of the political or the business world, but average citizens

who have access to the global communication network, and who thereby have the power to influence the direction of human history.

Political accountability, for one, is being considerably enhanced, because people are more free to 'blog' their views online, uncensored by restrictive governmental pressure and unfettered by main-line media propaganda and interests. This is tremendously helpful for NGOs who wish to network at the global level so as to put pressure on local governmental and business policies and practices. It is precisely such a network which can influence public opinion and lead to the denial of political status to tyrants who think they may adopt totalitarian or double standards in one country and get away with them in another. The denial of a visa to Narendra Modi to visit the U.S.A. is a good example of the power of this global network.¹⁸ With its power to disseminate relevant and widespread information, the internet is beginning to function as a propitious shaming mechanism and needs to be put to full use towards this end, whenever necessary.

Globalization will lead to the emergence of a democratic mentality, not because of the messianic missionary drive on the part of some powerful nations to colonize parts of the world in the name of democracy (which will more likely do a disservice to the spirit of democracy), but simply because democratic processes will increasingly be seen to be beneficial in terms of the common good. This is happening in India, especially in the cities, but also in the rural areas, when more and more citizens' groups are compelling state and metropolitan governmental authorities to be more accountable. The fructification and the optimal use of the RTI (Right to Information) Act is a good example of this emergence of the democratic spirit at the level of the ordinary citizen.

It is this process of the rapid and widespread dissemination of information that will bring about social transformation and accountability much more quickly than in the past. In his book, *Development As Freedom*, Amartya Sen argues that no famine has ever taken place in the history of the world in a functioning democracy.¹⁹ According to his analysis, economic disasters like famines more easily take place under the following circumstances: when government leaders and workers largely belong to the upper class, when there is less

accountability of the leaders to the people they govern, when there is a greater centralization of authority, where there is a lack of an adequate political opposition, when there is rigid censorship which entails a lack of freedom of expression and freedom of the press, where there is a desire to fudge information, to conceal accurate data, and to misinform people. One can easily see how many of these factors can only survive when the dissemination of information and social analyses are limited and restricted. But this is not possible in our contemporary situation. Consequently, it will be more and more difficult for non-democratic governments to function in an irresponsible and autocratic manner. Even if countries are not technically democratic, they will increasingly become only nominally non-democratic republics, as is the case in China, where totalitarian practices are compelled to be less harsh, as compared to the past.

A greater sense of democratization has also resulted in greater corporate social responsibility on the part of a good number of TNCs, whereby corporations are increasingly recognizing the contributory role they need to assume in civic affairs. CSR (corporate social responsibility) has become the buzz word in many corporate offices, but for various motives. Some corporations use the opportunity for image building, while others only reluctantly and marginally enter into this process. A few, however, recognize that if business has to succeed, corporations need to get involved in the process of building up a better social and civic infrastructure.²⁰

In this regard, what is remarkable is the establishment of the world's largest philanthropic endowment by the world's richest couple, viz., the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation. What was even more consoling this past year was the fact that the second richest person, Warren Buffet, has added to the monetary volume of this already immense foundation. According to the official website of the Foundation, the mission statement reads as follows:

Guided by the belief that every life has equal value, the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation works to reduce inequities and improve lives around the world. In developing countries, it focuses on improving health, reducing extreme poverty, and increasing access to technology in public libraries. In the United

States, the foundation seeks to ensure that all people have access to a great education and to technology in public libraries. In its local region, it focuses on improving the lives of low-income families.²¹

One of the reasons for engaging in such charitable ventures may be in order that business interests are strengthened rather than minimized in the future, because of a betterment of human standards of living, and hence better consumer education and buying power. But perhaps a deeper motivation is the realization of the sheer imbalance which constitutes contemporary global capitalism, which allows some people to make such obscene sums of money to be spent in vulgar opulence while others have to struggle to barely survive in hostile and subhuman conditions. It is a pity, however, that it is often (voluntary) charity and not forces of social and distributive justice which lies at the heart of such social projects.

Whether it is justice or charity which contributes towards the furthering of transnational responsibility, it is clear that transnational religions have a pivotal role in cultivating this virtue. As the sense of community within such religions is often transcontinental, there is a need to generate a concomitant sense of responsibility for the welfare of others within the community who need help in terms of integral welfare. Furthermore, while charity may begin at home, it ought not to end at home, but rather be extended to all, especially those who are in most need. Indeed, in an ideal global and virtual community, home is everywhere and everyone is a member of our home.

Over the past few years, the theologian Hans Kueng, along with others, has worked on the outlines of a 'global ethic' which would not only serve to unite believers and non-believers on the level of ethical theory, but, more importantly, serve to relate transcendent principles, whether religious or secular, with concrete projects connected with social development.²² Whatever be the merits or demerits of such a project, it is the likes of such a mentality which is necessary to usher in a new consciousness more fitting for the new world of globalization. Such a mentality can only arise from minds and hearts which are dominated by the spirit of hope and optimism, rather than that of despair or cynicism.

5. Pro-active optimism

Globalization has little room for 'naysayers' and cynics. NGOs and religious believers sometimes take a bleak view of the transnational, globalizing corporate world, as if it is an inhuman monster about to devour whole peoples and civilizations. On the other hand, the corporate world and Governmental agencies often consider NGOs and religious-based ethical protest as an unnecessary hindrance on the sure pathway towards development. There is need to overcome this polarization and work together towards a common future. Constructive criticism while working together is not only welcome but necessary. But there is no room for pessimism, and worse, cynicism. Instead, what is needed is a realistic, optimistic and futuristic approach towards development.

A realistic approach enables one to sacrifice one's ideological presuppositions and prejudices if they are not consonant with new developments. For example, the struggle towards economic development in West Bengal is a good indication whether the State is ready to participate in the process of globalization or not. The Party which has claimed to best represent the interests of the workers and the proletariat is forced to do a tightrope walk between past ideology on the one hand and pressing concerns for present and future development on the other. Party leaders who have had the chance to visit neighbouring China are in a good position to rethink their priorities in terms of development. However, it is difficult to be inspired by the Chinese model (which is a top-down State-controlled one) when one has to work with the Indian model which is more democratic. That is why the State Government is under pressure to reconsider methods of landgrabbing as evidenced in the recent Singur and Nandigram peasant protests. The Chief Minister, while regretting the use of force on the part of the Government and party cadres, has however made it quite clear that a primary reliance on agricultural labour will only result in backwardness. Such an admission clearly favouring industrialization and globalization from a Communist leader would be unthinkable a few years ago. Today, however, it bears testimony to the power of globalization, and the necessity to reinterpret one's principles if one is to survive, or better, flourish, in such a world.

Similarly, with regard to language, some who are overly patriotic have resisted the use of English as a medium of instruction in India (this of course does not include those who hypocritically do so for politically convenient reasons). However, many Indians of the lowest social classes, especially in urban areas, seem to prefer an English-medium education if they can afford it, for the future of their children stands to gain if they can be educated in a globally-recognized and competitive medium. Ideological convictions are necessary, but one must be ready to reinterpret them in the light of new developments, if one is to make progress.

Where environmental development is concerned, the future is in some sense more important than the present. This is an area where unbridled global capitalism coupled with cheap technology and weak political resolve can cause havoc, and lead to dramatic climate change even in our own age, as is already happening worldwide. If realistic and futuristic measures are not adopted in a reasonable manner, the span and quality of human life (to say nothing of non-human life) will considerably reduce. Wisdom demands that sacrifices be made by all, not only by a few, so that future generations may profit. For example, while China is producing cheap goods for the West, but by using methods of primitive energy generation, it is imperative that both China and the West need to sacrifice – China in terms of investing in better and ecologically safer technology both in terms of energy production and the manufacturing of goods, and the West by paying a coal tax (or energy tax in general) towards adequate monetary compensation for Chinese-manufactured goods, so as to partially cover these costs.²³

Finally, with regard to the future, religion is one of those social institutions which are best suited to generate optimism and hope. All religions are based on narratives which end with some form of salvific or liberative situation. This is similar to other forms of developmental models, whether economic, political, cultural or educational. But religious myths, belief-systems, rituals and a sense of community place religion in a privileged and opportune position, both to generate hope among its adherents as well as to inject hope into the collective consciousness of humankind. What is needed is a conscious effort to relate religion with social development, so as to

both guide the current forces of globalization in a proper direction, and to provide motivation to work towards social change, not only among believers, but together with all people of good will.

Conclusion

Globalization is not a perfect example of social development, as numerous studies based on teleological and deontological considerations have demonstrated. However, whether we like globalization or not, as a social force it has come to stay, at least over the near future. We have to learn how to sublimate its productive energies into more salubrious channels and how to address and rectify its less integrally developmental dimensions.

Religion as a social force has a lot to offer in this regard. By cultivating relevant contemporary moral dispositions or virtues among its adherents (and I have focused on just five), believers can work along with people of other faiths and non-believers alike to make globalization a humane experience for all rather than a monstrous experience for a sizeable section of humanity. This ability of religion to be a resource for the cultivation of virtues for our contemporary age needs to be realized desperately today. If religion does not rise to this challenge, it will not be able to take its rightful place among the different social forces which are currently helping to shape human destiny. Not to be involved in human history towards this end is not to be true to one's sacred vocation. We live in the hope that the different religions will together rise to the occasion in the service of a global human family.

Notes

1. Virtue ethics is traditionally associated with the ethical approach of Aristotle, as compared to deontological ethics, which is associated with Kant and those who subscribe to some form of natural law, while teleological ethics is associated with the British Utilitarian philosophers.
2. See John Kline, *Ethics for International Business: Decision Making in a Global Political Economy*, Routledge, 2005, where the author discusses various aspects of globalization from an ethical perspective, especially from deontological and teleological concerns.

3. See my article, "Mutual Challenges to Religion and Globalization," in Institute of Indian Culture Newsletter, Mumbai, July 2006.
4. *Making Globalization Good: The Moral Challenges of Global Capitalism*, ed. John Dunning; Oxford University Press, 2003. In this work, there is an attempt to relate this process of globalization and global capitalism with primary ethical and religious movements and institutions. Specific Chapters are devoted to the relationship between globalization and the major religions, including 'Eastern Religions.
5. John Dunning, "The Moral Imperatives of Global Capitalism – An Overview," in *Making Globalization Good*, p.12.
6. *Ibid.*, p. 13.
7. Joseph, Stiglitz, "Towards a New Paradigm of Development," in *Making Globalization Good*, p.76. Stiglitz is a Nobel Laureate in Economics, who famously stepped down as the Chief Economist and Senior Vice-President of the World Bank in 2000. His books include *Globalization and Its Discontents*, W.W. Norton, 2001, and more recently, *Making Globalization Work—the Next Steps to Social Justice*, W.W. Norton and Allen Lane (Penguin), 2006.
8. See the document, *Globalization and Marginalization – Our Global Apostolic Response*, brought out by the Jesuit Social Justice Secretariat in Rome, 2006, which argues towards this end.
9. The terms MNC (multi-national corporation), TNC (trans-national corporation), MNE (multi-national enterprise) and 'supranational companies' are used to describe the same reality, viz., business interests and projects which span nations and continents in order to produce and distribute goods and services mainly for profit.
10. A good example of exaggerated rhetoric leading to futile action is the war in Iraq. It was ostensibly based on the claim of weapons of mass destruction, which the 'embedded' American media rhetorically supported right from the inception of the bellicose discourse, systematically obfuscating the truth. This war in Iraq is one of the more pressing international hindrances towards global development, with not only economic but even interreligious overtones of disharmony.
11. See *Globalization and its Victims – As Seen by its Victims*, edited by Michael Amaladoss, S.J., Delhi, Vidyajyoti/ISPCK, 1999, for a broad analysis of how irresponsible globalization has the potentiality to generate a wide variety of 'victims.
12. J. Orstrom Moller, "Wanted: A New Strategy for Globalization," *The Futurist*, Vo.38, Jan 2004. p.20ff. Moller was Ambassador of Den-

mark to Singapore, and is one who argues that globalization is resulting in a greater divide between the haves and have-nots and, if unbridled, will result in an ascendancy of nationalism (to safeguard local interests) rather than internationalism.

13. See Amartya Sen, *Identity and Violence – The Illusion of Destiny*, London, Allen Lane (Penguin), 2006.
14. A good example is *Wikipedia*, the free (and perhaps fastest-growing) online encyclopedia started in 2001, to which anyone is free to contribute. But besides this, there are numerous medical and engineering problems which are placed on the internet eliciting responses and solutions, to say nothing of chatrooms and blogsites which allow free expression and interaction on almost every aspect of human existence.
15. Archbishop Desmond Tutu received the Nobel Peace Prize in 1984, while Amartya Sen received the Nobel Prize for Economic Science in 1998.
16. The full summary statement of the “International Conference on Religion and Globalization” is edited by Ruben Habito, and may be found in *Buddhist-Christian Studies*, 24 (2004) 241ff. This statement covers the most significant areas which relate the promise and the problems of globalization on the one hand with the power and the limitations of religious resources on the other.
17. Amartya Sen, “How to Judge Globalism,” *The American Prospect*, Vol.13, Issue.1 (2002) p. 2ff.
18. Narendra Modi will go down in history as the Chief Minister who was primarily responsible for the pogrom against the Muslims in his state. Indeed, his strategy of communally divisive politics has been poignantly referred to as the ‘Gujarat experiment,’ perhaps intended to be the precursor of a Nazi-like ‘final solution’ of some of the minorities in India.
19. Amartya Sen, *Development as Freedom*, Oxford University Press, 2001.
20. See, for example, the DNA (Daily News and Analysis), Mumbai, report of December 15, 2006, p.1, which is titled, “Private Sector Wants to Maintain City – Corporations Will Adopt Municipal Wards and Help in Their Upkeep.”
21. <http://www.gatesfoundation.org/MediaCenter/FactSheet/>
22. See <http://astro.temple.edu/~dialogue/Antho/kung.htm> for an outline of this global ethic project.
23. See “The Coal Trap,” *Newsweek*, January 15, 2007, in which this point is argued.